

DAMAGE AND FAILURE OF THERMOPLASTIC LAMINATES WITH LAYER-LIKE AND BUNDLE-LIKE FIBER CLUSTERS

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Keywords: Thermoplastic composite, Debonding, Transverse crack

ABSTRACT

We study the effect of fiber spatial distributions on damage and failure of thermoplastic laminates (glass/polypropylene, GF/PP). Tensile test on unidirectional laminates of $[0]_4$ and $[90]_8$ was performed to obtain the mechanical properties, and to observe the failure of GF/PP. To study the property degradation, load/unload tests on cross-ply laminates of $[0/90_n]_s$ with different variations of n were carried out. We also propose a micromechanical framework to simulate the effect of layer-like and bundle-like clusters on the global stress-strain response of unidirectional laminate.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic composites reinforced with continuous fibers have been applied for automotive structures for their fast processing time, recyclability and excellent impact performance. Often, the tapes used to produce thermoplastic composites come with an inherent factor that would remain unchanged during processing at a certain temperature, pressure and dwell time. One of the factors, which also imply the quality of the microstructure, is fiber spatial distribution. Fiber spatial distribution may determine the mechanical performance of thermoplastic composites since the damage and failure mechanisms can be changed [1]. Attempts to simulate the fiber spatial distribution are also reported in Refs. [2, 3].

In this paper, we studied the effect of layer-like and bundle-like fiber clusters within glass/polypropylene (GF/PP) tapes on the mechanical properties and damage behaviour of GF/PP composites through experiments and modelling schemes. The objectives are two-fold: (i) to study the effect of layer-like and bundle-like fiber distributions on damage in unidirectional and cross-ply laminates, (ii) to propose a micromechanical model that would facilitate the damage analysis of UD laminates.

We would first describe the experimental part which consists of (i) direct tensile tests on unidirectional laminates of $[0]_4$ and $[90]_8$, (ii) load/unload tests on cross-ply laminates of $[0/90]_s$, $[0/90_2]_s$ and $[0/90_4]_s$, where we would show the stiffness degradation in cross-ply laminates. In the modeling part, we show a modeling strategy using representative volume element (multi-fiber within a matrix phase) to simulate global response of unidirectional GF/PP. We would provide a comparison of stress-strain curves between simulation and experiments.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Materials

Thermoplastic materials considered herein are glass-fiber reinforced polypropylene composites. The fiber is of E-glass, whilst the matrix is polypropylene. Glass/polypropylene composite comes in the form of unidirectional tape with typical thickness of 250 μm . GF/PP tapes from two different suppliers were acquired. The so-called Material-A has a fiber volume fraction (V_f) of 45%, while the Material-B has V_f of 35%. We stacked and processed a number of tapes to manufacture unidirectional [0] laminates. The processing of GF/PP laminate was done using steel mold, which was compressed using a hot press (Pinette Emidecau Industries 15T) at 7.5 bar. The temperature was raised from 30°C to 210°C, and kept at 210°C for 20 minutes. The cooling rate was set at 22°C/min. Cross-sectioning was performed on the finished plaque, and the preliminary observation shows that two unique fiber spatial distributions were found. Material-A shows a layer-like fiber clusters (see Fig. 1, left) while the Material-B shows a bundle-like fiber clusters (Fig. 1, right). This kind of clustering is actually coming from the original tape itself. It means that fiber clustering was not entirely removed, and remains more or less the same even after the manufacturing process. It is important to note that the polypropylene used in Material-A is copolymer, where the neat polypropylene properties have been obtained in separately. As for Material-B, unfortunately the properties of polypropylene (assumed to be homopolymer) are unknown. In all, the difference between Material-A and Material-B is not only in terms of fiber clustering, but also in terms of polypropylene types.

Figure 1: Two types of fiber cluster found in GF/PP laminates: layer-like (Material-A) and bundle-like (Material-B) fiber clusters

2.2 Specimens

Specimens for direct tensile test have the following dimensions: [0]₄ laminates (250 mm long, 15 mm wide, 1 mm thick, 134 mm gauge length), [90]₈ laminates (110 mm long, 20 mm wide, 2 mm thick, 70 mm gauge length). Specimens for cross-ply laminates of [0/90]_s, [0/90₂]_s and [0/90₄]_s have following dimension: 110 mm long, 20 mm wide, 70 mm gauge length. The thickness is 1 mm for [0/90]_s, 1.5 mm for [0/90₂]_s and 2.5 mm for [0/90₄]_s. Glass/epoxy tabs were glued onto the specimen ends using acrylic adhesive (3M Scotch Weld).

2.2 Experimental procedures

Both monotonic and cyclic (load/unload) tensile tests were carried out using Instron 5882 (100 kN load cell), which was equipped with video extensometer for strain measurement. Direct test carried out on [0]₄ and [90]₈ was performed at the loading rate of 2 mm/min (ASTM D3039) to obtain stress-strain curves. Direct test on cross-ply laminates was performed at 0.5 mm/min. Direct test was performed until the specimen failed, where the failure morphology was carefully noted. Load/unload displacement-controlled tensile test was carried out with following increments: 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4, 1.6, 1.8 and 2.0 mm, where 0.2 mm corresponds to approximately 0.2% strain. This load/unload test aims to obtain stiffness degradation, and provides the macroscopic damage behaviour in cross-ply laminates.

3 MODELING

3.1 Determination of RVE for layer-like and bundle-like fiber clusters

A special care should be granted to the determination of representative volume element (RVE) considering the complexity of GF/PP microstructures with layer-like and bundle-like fiber clusters. Here we determine the RVEs from the geometrical analysis (using two-point probability functions) and from the mechanical analysis (by calculating the eigenvalues of the homogenized elastic tensor) [4]. For each fiber cluster, the analyses were carried out on five optical microscopy images that have been binarized. From both analyses, the critical RVE sizes are found to be $250 \times 250 \times 250 \mu\text{m}^3$ for layer-like clusters and $400 \times 400 \times 400 \mu\text{m}^3$ for bundle-like cluster, respectively.

3.2 Finite element models

3D RVEs consist of perfectly circular fibres and matrix that are developed in ABAQUS Standard. Fibres with non-uniform radii are spatially arranged according to the result of the RVEs determination. The average fiber radius is $16.32 \mu\text{m}$. The RVEs are then meshed with 8-node hexahedral element (C3D8R) with reduced integration point to avoid volumetric locking. Figure 3 shows the RVEs for layer-like and bundle-like clusters. V_f for layer-like and bundle-like models is 46.36% and 35.90%, respectively.

Figure 2: Critical size of RVEs for FE models of GF/PP with layer-like and bundle-like fiber clusters

3.3 Constitutive models

Fibres are modelled as linear elastic material ($E = 72 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu = 0.22$) while the polypropylene matrix follows isotropic elastic-plastic with pressure dependent behavior. The properties of polypropylene were obtained by conducting simple tensile test using dog-bone specimen (ISO 527-2 1BA) of neat polypropylene with the thickness of 2 mm. In this case, the polypropylene was the same with the one used for Material-A. Unfortunately, we could not obtain neat polypropylene used for making Material-B, which could be different from Material-A. Thus, for simulation of bundle-like

fiber clusters, we used neat PP properties of Material-A. Hyperbolic Drucker-Prager plasticity [5] was used to model pressure dependency of the matrix since it can handle convergence problem at high tensile stress level. At the moment, ductile damage behaviour and strain-rate dependent plasticity of polypropylene are not yet included in the model; but they will be included in the future model.

3.4 Periodical boundary condition

Periodical boundary conditions (PBCs) are applied to the RVE since the effective properties derived under these conditions for a finite RVE is always closer to that of an infinite RVE than those obtained under traction or displacement conditions [1]. Since the RVEs obtained from RVE determination analysis are not having periodical microstructures, PBCs cannot be applied directly. Therefore, adjustment is needed especially for fibres which are intersected with RVE edges. First, initial fibre volume fraction is calculated. Then, the fibres that intersect with RVEs edges are removed. The reduction of V_f due to this removal is calculated. To compensate the reduction of V_f , the new fibres are added to the RVE by obeying two conditions: (i) the fibers are not overlapped with previously-prescribed fibres, and (ii) periodicity conditions must be satisfied.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Tensile behavior of $[0]_4$ and $[90]_8$ UD laminates: experimental results

The stress-strain curves of UD $[0]_4$ and $[90]_8$ for laminates with layer-like and bundle-like clusters can be seen in Fig. 1a and 1b, respectively. Mechanical properties calculated from the stress-strain curves are given in Table 1. The different trend of stress-strain curves in UD $[0]_4$ (Fig. 2a) is partly due to different V_f between Material-A (“layer-like”) and Material-B (“bundle-like”). Suppose that the stress-strain curves of “layer-like” specimens are normalized with respect to V_f , the effect of fiber spatial distribution would not be so strong. Likewise, stress-strain behavior in layer-like and bundle-like fibers in transverse direction (Fig. 2b) does not show sensitivity to the fiber distributions. Failure in $[0]_4$ of specimens with both fiber distributions are characterized with the same mechanism: fiber splitting and fiber fracture. Transverse failure of $[90]_8$ in specimens with “bundle-like” fibers typically traverses the clusters (see Fig. 3, right), which is different from that with “layer-like” fibers (Fig. 3, left).

Properties		Layer-like cluster	Bundle-like cluster
Resin material	-	PP (copolymer)	PP (unknown type)
Fiber volume fraction	[%]	41 - 45	34 - 39
Ultimate strength of $[0]_4$	[GPa]	699 ± 9	656 ± 49
Failure strain of $[0]_4$	[%]	2.12 ± 0.04	3.04 ± 0.10
Ultimate strength of $[90]_8$	[GPa]	16.8 ± 0.8	19.7 ± 1.4
Failure strain of $[90]_8$	[%]	0.51 ± 0.11	0.49 ± 0.07
Longitudinal modulus	[GPa]	34.8 ± 1.3	26.8 ± 1.6
Transverse modulus	[GPa]	5.47 ± 0.67	6.06 ± 0.49

Table 1: Mechanical properties of GF/PP.

Figure 2: Stress-strain curves of UD GF/PP laminate: (a) $[0]_4$, (b) $[90]_8$

Figure 3: Failure in UD $[90]_8$ GF/PP laminate

4.2 Tensile behavior of $[0]_4$ and $[90]_8$ UD laminates: micromechanical modeling results

Comparison between simulation and experiments for GF/PP $[0]$ with layer-like and bundle-like fiber clusters is shown in Fig. 4. The simulation for this case is terminated between strain levels of 2.2 and 3.2%, respectively. Simulation results are in a good agreement with the experiments. This indicates that the RVEs developed for both fiber distributions are reasonable.

Figure 4: Stress-strain curves of $[0]_4$: comparison between simulation and experiments

Fig. 5 shows that the comparison of stress-strain curves of GF/PP $[90]$ between simulation and experiment is in a fair agreement. The simulation was terminated at the strain level of 0.8%. Generally, the difference of stress-strain curves in $[90]_8$ could be due to absence of damage model within matrix and fiber/matrix interfaces, different variations of fiber volume fraction, absence of strain-rate dependent plasticity of polypropylene, different type of polypropylene being used and

transverse isotropy of the glass fibers. It should be mentioned that in the simulation the property used for the matrix in both layer-like and bundle-like fiber clusters is the same, which is neat PP of Material-A. Possibly the higher measured transverse modulus for Material-B would be the result of a higher matrix modulus as would be typically found for PP homopolymer materials.

Figure 5: Stress-strain curves of $[90]_8$: comparison between simulation and experiments

4.3 Tensile behavior of cross-ply laminates: experimental results

Fig. 6 shows that cross-ply laminates with bundle-like fiber clusters have lower stiffness than that with layer-like fiber clusters. Since the tensile response of cross-ply laminates is mainly determined by the 0° fibers, lower fiber volume fraction in Material-B would consequently lead to a lower stiffness. It is important to note that specimen-2 (black line) in Fig. 6 (right) has lower strength due to fiber waviness in 0° fibers of the sample.

Results of load/unload tests are shown in the form of stiffness degradation shown in Fig. 7. Fig. 7 shows that generally the stiffness for both layer-like and bundle-like specimens is reduced at similar rate. Effect of fiber clustering on the stiffness degradation derived from load/unload tests is not obvious. Acoustic emission analysis will be carried out in the future to understand if fiber clustering has an effect on the internal damage mechanisms [6].

Figure 6: Stress-strain curves of cross-ply laminates

Figure 7: Stiffness degradation in cross-ply laminates with different 90° ply-thickness

5 CONCLUSIONS

The effect of fiber spatial distribution on tensile properties and damage in unidirectional composites and cross-ply laminates glass/polypropylene composites is studied. Layer-like and bundle-like fiber clusters found in glass/polypropylene are investigated through experiments and modeling. It is found that longitudinal stiffness of GF/PP [0] with layer-like fiber clusters is higher than that with bundle-like clusters, but this is mainly due to higher fiber volume fraction in “layer-like” GF/PP. Effect of layer-like and bundle-like clusters is negligible in GF/PP [90]. Our RVEs are able to simulate longitudinal and transverse stress-strain responses of GF/PP with reasonably good accuracy. Improved models will be developed in the near future to include ductile damage and time-dependent plasticity of polypropylene.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors would like to thank SABIC for the research funding.

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